

SOCIAL SCIENCES

NICHE TOURISM - INNOVATIONS AND QUALITY CULTURE IN SPECIALIZED WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to analyze the advantages of Bulgaria's full educational vertical in wellness culture across two professional fields and assess the external evaluation of the knowledge, intellectual, and practical skills of specialized personnel in Bulgarian niche tourism. It emphasizes the significance of the studied indicators. **Methods:** We conducted a psychometric assessment of customer opinions to quantify their responses. This was achieved using an adaptive questionnaire administered through Google Drive. **Results:** The paper analyzes the benefits of accredited innovations in niche tourism. We developed new educational programs aligned with recent changes in Bulgarian educational and scientific policies. Over the past decade, Bulgaria has successfully integrated six specialized programs in niche tourism within two professional categories: Healthcare and Sport, and is establishing a Centre for Excellence. **Conclusions:** The identified patterns serve as a foundation for building a comprehensive educational framework from secondary to doctoral levels, focusing on innovative programs that support smart services in niche tourism and a knowledge-based economy in Bulgaria.

Keywords: Education, innovative coaching, Niche tourism, professional competences, smart model, new job positions.

INTRODUCTION

The modern recreational sector and niche tourism market primarily cater to clients with dynamic lifestyles who seek effective and rapid recovery options (1, 2). These clients often require deep relaxation, recreation, and re-energisation through intelligent therapies utilizing natural products and a balanced daily routine to promote a healthy lifestyle (3). From 2017 to 2018, there was a significant increase in vacations focused on wellness destinations that offer health packages. However, a global shortage of specialised staff poses a challenge (4). According to the Global Wellness Institute, approximately 180,000 qualified personnel with the necessary skills and knowledge in tourism are lacking (5). The same study highlighted an urgent need for specialized training programs across various educational levels to prepare staff, from operational roles to management positions. The recreational industry and niche tourism collectively serve over 4 billion people worldwide, contributing to a global Recreational industry that generates more than 300 billion euros in revenue each year (6, 7).

There is no comprehensive statistical data on the total revenue of the wellness and spa industry across the Balkans (8, 9). The sector faces an urgent need for innovative marketing strategies and modern management approaches to enhance its global competitiveness (10, 11). Additionally, the recreational industry and niche tourism require a new theoretical framework that integrates digitalisation and intelligent services (12, 13). Bulgaria boasts a rich tradition in thermal tourism and is consistently ranked among the top five countries worldwide for the diversity and vitality of its mineral waters, which vary in temperature, physical properties, and chemical composition (14, 15). However, despite this natural wealth, the wellness and spa sectors in Bulgaria still lack a clearly defined vision, structured regulations, and standardized requirements (16). There is

also a shortage of highly skilled professionals in the field—specialists who possess strong multilingual communication abilities to meet the demands of international clientele (17, 18). This paper presents accredited and successfully implemented innovations aimed at supporting the recreational industry and niche tourism. In response to recent changes in Bulgarian educational and scientific policies, specialized educational and certification programs have been developed and integrated into practice. Between 2007 and 2019, Bulgaria emerged as a European leader in scientific and educational advancements by establishing six specialized programs in niche tourism across two professional fields—Healthcare and Sport. Through the Erasmus+ (KA2) program, a new European profession, Wellness Instructor, was officially introduced. In February 2018, Bulgaria secured funding for the development of the Centre of Excellence "Heritage BG", prioritizing creative and recreational industries under the Operational Program "Science and Education for Smart Growth", co-financed by the European Structural and Investment Funds (2014–2020) (19).

As a result, Bulgaria became the first country to establish and accredit a complete educational pathway in Wellness, Spa, and Thalasso Culture—spanning from secondary education to doctoral studies. Simultaneously, the country built the highest-level scientific infrastructure in Europe for this field: The Bulgarian Centre for Excellence in Creative and Recreation Industries ("Heritage BG"). Within this institution, a specialized research body was established, focusing on Social Innovations, Recreational Human Design, and Niche Tourism, further solidifying Bulgaria's leadership in this domain.

METHODS

The study involved 110 Bulgarian participants (ages 18–36), including 33 owners or managers of wellness & spa centers, scholars, bachelor's, master's, and doctoral graduates in wellness, spa, and thalasso culture. The group consisted of 37 men and 40 women, with a median age of 27.6. Instead of classifying by educational level, participants were divided into three experience-based segments: less than three years, four to seven years, and eight years or more. Job positions ranged from CEOs and managers to operational employees and non-graduates in the field. The study was conducted at the National Sports Academy, Sofia (2023–2024), with informed consent obtained for data publication. As part of the 7.5 Healthcare and 7.6 Sport accredited professional fields, psychometric measurements were applied (February–November 2024) to assess the opinions of graduates, teachers, and students. The responses were ranked to evaluate the quality of education and the effectiveness of newly integrated programs at the bachelor and secondary school levels. This research serves as a certification tool for assessing professional competencies in Bulgarian niche tourism and supports staff at recreation centers. The primary goal is to analyze the advantages of Bulgaria's full educational vertical in wellness culture while establishing an external evaluation system for specialized personnel, focusing on their knowledge, intellectual, and practical skills. The goal of the study is to analyse the advantages in the Bulgarian full educational vertical in wellness culture, in two professional fields and establish the external evaluation for proposed knowledge, intellectual and practical skills of specialised personnel

in Bulgarian niche tourism by defining the importance of the studied indicators.

RESULTS

For the first time, Bulgaria's educational and scientific achievements in wellness and spa are being highlighted. The Center for Excellence in Creative and Recreation Industry ("Heritage BG") features a state-of-the-art laboratory modeled on global research on water's health benefits and Bulgaria's accredited educational model for training specialized staff in wellness and niche tourism. This initiative attracts young professionals to Bulgaria through specialized bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs aligned with newly established job positions in the national classification (NCP, 2014): Spa Center Manager/Advisor (ID: 1431-6022), Wellness Center Manager (ID: 1431-6023), and Thalasso Center Manager (ID: 1431-6024). Bulgaria leads Europe with its first doctoral program in Wellness – Health Promotion, a bachelor's program in Wellness Advising (since July 2019), and specialized high school education in Technology and Entrepreneurship in Wellness and Niche Tourism (since December 2018).

Two integrated figures illustrate Bulgaria's education and research advancements:

➤ Figure 1 outlines accredited wellness and recreation programs from high school to doctoral levels at NSA "V. Levski."

➤ Figure 2 The succession of decisions, actions, and reforms for the transformation of Bulgaria into a global centre for Recreation industry.

Figure 1. The Bulgarian education & science model for the Wellness & Spa & Thalasso culture.

For the first time, two full educational verticals in niche tourism (fields 7.6. Sport and 7.5. Health Care) have been introduced. Students engage in volunteer programs and collaborations through NSA "V. Levski" and networks like Blue Cluster and Cluster Bridge, promoting a healthy lifestyle and responsible water use. The mission is to foster a culture of sustainable water management and position Bulgaria as a global leader in wellness and spa innovation. Through international forums and scientific advancements, the goal is to transform Bulgaria into the "Silicon Valley of Water," promoting health prevention, education, and a knowledge-based economy.

A new intellectual and scientific infrastructure is being developed in Sofia, incorporating Aquaphotomics, a global innovation by Bulgarian scientist Prof. Rumiana Tsenkova, D.Sc. For the first time in Bulgaria, scientific innovation standards, creative business models, and strategic instruments have been implemented to drive new policies in the wellness and spa sector. These innovations promote international collaboration on education quality and water use for health, longevity, and therapy.

✓ The Center for Excellence "Heritage BG" will lead an extensive informational campaign at national and international levels, leveraging media, businesses, government, and educational institutions to promote

the benefits of water-based health solutions. Bulgaria introduces a new global initiative: Wellness for Everyone – Healthy Lifestyle for All, aligning with EU priorities (2014-2020) for creative and recreation industries. Key objectives include: Expanding global career opportunities for young professionals in the wellness and spa industry through the Blue Cluster youth movement.

✓ Using online events to promote quality standards in wellness education, products, and services while encouraging citizens to adopt a healthy lifestyle.

✓ Establishing transparent policies on water use for health prevention and therapy, leveraging the unique properties of Bulgarian mineral waters.

This data, based on official accreditation documentation, reflects the author's direct involvement in developing the model and leading research initiatives for the new Center for Excellence. The vertical upgrade follows a structured approach, integrating European best practices and insights from education policy shifts over the past decade. Market analyses identified key trends in the recreation and niche tourism industries, forming the basis for a ten-year action plan aligned with Bulgaria's education and science priorities.

Documentation includes expert analyses of EU and Bulgarian education laws, accreditation standards, and professional competencies, ensuring alignment with European qualification frameworks. Scientific

studies focus on EU research priorities, guiding innovation in education.

Figure 2. The succession of decisions, actions, and reforms for the transformation of Bulgaria into a global centre for Recreation industry.

This experience led to the development of a doctoral program, successfully accredited with a score of 9.2/10. A project was then structured to equip an experimental laboratory for Social Innovations, Recreation Human Design, and Niche Tourism as part of the Heritage BG Center of Excellence. Funded through the EU Operational Program Education & Science for Intelligent Growth (2014-2020), the initiative secured financial backing from the EU, Bulgarian government, and social funds. According to Ellis (2013), key challenges in Wellness industry management include:

- ✚ Training current and future Spa and Wellness managers.
- ✚ Developing high-level skills for career advancement.
- ✚ Addressing interdisciplinary skill gaps in health culture and motivation.

Figure 2 illustrates the broader socioeconomic impact of EU investments in research and innovation, providing a platform for institutions and professionals to showcase best practices.

Heritage BG aims to encourage industry professionals to apply experimental results effectively, bridging science and business to maximize societal impact. A key goal is fostering business investment in research, ensuring scientific findings translate into practical applications with economic and social benefits.

The Center for Excellence showcases the socioeconomic value of government and EU investments in research and innovation. It supports young scientists in utilizing their findings for knowledge-based growth, influencing policy, commercialising services, launching startups, or setting new standards. The Bulgarian Heritage BG Center for Excellence is designed to address national, regional (Balkan), and European needs in recreation and niche tourism, with long-term impacts on society, economy, and policy. Its success is measured by how effectively scientific research contributes to solving social challenges while driving economic and health advancements.

Figure 3. Expert ranking of indicators considering the requirements of efficiency services in the recreation centre

The project received support from the United Nations World Tourism Organization, emphasizing the role of research in enhancing quality in niche tourism. The consortium includes eight research institutes and four universities, bringing together over 230 experts, including 22 young scientists from NSA "V. Levski". The assessment results (see Fig. 1) highlight key priorities for Wellness & SPA centers. The top-ranked factor is the need for innovation to enhance customer well-being (753 units – 88%), followed by compliance with National and EU quality standards (673 units – 63%). The third and fourth most significant indicators are "Well-trained staff" (466 units – 68.5%) and the necessity of Smart equipment for effective service delivery (361 units – 44.5%). Reputation and management efficiency rank next, with scores of 309 units (71.5%) and 297 units (64.5%), respectively. Other important factors (7th–9th place) include optimal pricing strategies, diverse wellness and anti-aging services, flexible marketing policies, and favorable working conditions with career growth opportunities. Regarding Smart test usage (see Tab. 1), 50% of bachelor students value the ability to refine wellness knowledge via mobile devices (compared to 34% of master's students, 29% of owners/managers/PhD students, and 40% of scholars). Transparency in knowledge assessment is highly valued by owners/managers/PhD students (48%), followed by master's students (43%), bachelor students (42%), and scholars (48%).

DISCUSSION

The study on intellectual products for training new professions, "Wellness Advisor" and "Wellness Instructor," highlights key priorities. The Smart test for Wellness knowledge, preferred by 50% of respondents, confirms that innovation, Smart equipment, and qualified personnel are crucial for service quality. Respondents prioritized unified educational standards aligned with EU criteria and national certification requirements. Similar studies in Austria, Estonia, the UK, Serbia, Romania, and Macedonia revealed an urgent need for specialised Niche tourism training programs. Future professionals in Recreation and Wellness require strong knowledge, organisational skills, and expertise in holistic and natural health approaches. Motivation to deliver quality wellness services and promote a healthy lifestyle is essential for improving national well-being.

Strengthening collaboration between academic institutions, vocational training centers, and industry is vital to bridge theory and practice in the recreation sector. Under our scientific leadership, the Erasmus+ KA2 project supports these goals. The issued intellectual products are rated with a high significance for adding value to the educational and labour politics in the EU which are expected to secure intellectual growth. The 5 new Wellness & Spa & Thalasso programs from Bachelor until doctoral degree in two professional majors were successfully accredited and highly valued by the experts in the National agency for evaluation and accreditation (NAEA): 7.5 health care and 7.6 sports. The presented innovative and stable educational and scientific model is incorporated in the National sports academy "V. Levski" which proves its position as an educational leader on a national, regional and European level.

CONCLUSIONS

The research highlights several key implications for the recreation industry and its educational development:

1. At the European level, there is a growing need for well-trained professionals with specialized education in recreation, wellness, and spa management at both high school and university levels.
2. The Bulgarian model offers seven accredited programs designed to train both operational staff and managers in Wellness, Spa, and Thalasso services, emphasizing high-level skills and expertise.
3. In Europe and the Balkans, managerial roles in the recreation industry require interdisciplinary knowledge, combining business management with wellness culture to promote healthier lifestyles.
4. Bulgaria has demonstrated its potential as a leading educational hub for the Recreation industry and Niche tourism in the Balkan region.
5. European standards emphasize high-quality education and professional competencies, ensuring that specialized personnel in the recreation and niche tourism sectors meet rigorous industry requirements.

These findings reinforce the need for continuous advancements in education, training, and industry collaboration to enhance the quality and impact of wellness and recreation services across Europe.

Note:

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest was declared by the author and the institution.

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An agreement for informed consent to publishing data was signed.

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